

LINKING DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS to FINANCIAL INCLUSION OUTCOMES in TANZANIA

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Abstract

This study investigates how demographic factors shape financial services in Tanzania, focusing on age, gender, income, education, and place of residence. By using an approach of the mixed methods, the research combines primary data from 400 survey participants with complementary findings from the FinScope Tanzania 2023 survey. Descriptive and inferential analyses were used to examine how different groups access and use formal, semi-formal, and informal financial services. The results show steady progress in financial inclusion, with about 85% of respondents reporting ownership of a formal financial account. Much of this improvement is linked to the widespread use of the mobile money, which has made financial inclusion more accessible, useful and convenient. However, this progress is uneven. Women, older adults, low-income households, people with limited education, and rural communities still face higher levels of exclusion. These gaps are influenced by persistent barriers such as low financial literacy, high transaction costs, weak service infrastructure, and policies that do not fully address the needs of underserved groups. Although digital finance has broadened access, technology by itself cannot close all existing divides. Reducing these gaps requires addressing both demographic and structural challenges that limit meaningful participation in the financial system. The study recommends expanding financial education programs, promoting gender-responsive financial solutions, and increasing investment in digital and physical infrastructure. Ensuring that policies reflect the realities of different demographic groups is essential for building a fairer and more inclusive financial landscape in Tanzania.

Keywords: *demographic factors; financial inclusion; digital finance; financial literacy; gender disparity.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Financial inclusion has become an increasingly a central element in efforts to build inclusive economies and improve livelihoods, particularly in developing regions. It is not just about having a bank account; it is about ensuring people can actively and responsibly engage with financial tools like savings, credit, payments, and insurance. The services offered must be affordable, trustworthy, and tailored to real-life needs (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2023; World Bank, 2022). True inclusion empowers individuals to manage risks, build assets, and improve their livelihoods. The Global Findex Database (2021) highlights how digital financial innovations, especially mobile money, have transformed financial access in Sub-Saharan Africa, creating new opportunities for groups that were once excluded.

In Tanzania, financial inclusion has become an essential policy priority aimed at fostering inclusive economic growth and reducing poverty. Insights from the FinScope Tanzania 2023 Survey, carried out by Financial Sector Deepening Trust (FSDT) and the Bank of Tanzania (BoT), illustrate substantial progress. The proportion of adults accessing formal financial services has grown significantly, rising from 44 percent in 2009 to 76 percent in 2023 (FSDT & BoT, 2023). This growth has been largely driven by mobile money and agent banking, which have expanded financial access across both urban and rural areas (FSDT & BoT, 2023). The Bank of Tanzania (2022) attributes this success to continued financial reforms and liberalization that opened the sector to private and foreign investors. As a result, Tanzania now has a competitive and diversified system of 46 licensed banks and a strong network of mobile money operators serving people nationwide.

Despite these achievements, financial exclusion remains uneven across population groups. FinScope (2023) shows that 26 percent of women are still excluded compared to 17.9 percent of men. Folks residing in rural areas mainly face obstacles like low financial literacy, weak internet connectivity, and limited access to formal outlets. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2022), over 60 percent of Tanzanians are under 35 years old, and about 70 percent live in rural areas, indicating that the country's youthful and rural population strongly shapes both opportunities and challenges in achieving full inclusion.

Globally, studies show that gender, age, education, income, and location are key factors influencing financial inclusion (Allen et al., 2022; Noelia, 2019; Delvin, 2022). Younger, educated and individuals with high income mostly enjoy the use of formal and online financial systems, while women, the elderly, and rural populations often depend on informal systems. These differences reveal that financial inclusion is not just an economic or technological issue; it is also deeply social and demographic.

The rise of digital finance has further reshaped Tanzania's financial landscape. By 2023, the country had over 40 million registered mobile money accounts, placing it among Africa's digital finance leaders (GSMA, 2023). For the sake of communities living in rural areas and those with low income, mobile platforms have lowered access barriers purposely to make sure they join in formal financial institutions. Yet, many users still engage mainly in basic services such as money transfers and bill payments, with limited use of savings, credit, or insurance (GSMA, 2023; FSDT & BoT, 2023). Those with higher income and education tend to diversify their financial use, while others remain on the margins of meaningful inclusion.

Tanzania's push for financial inclusion connects directly with some of the world's biggest development goals. At its heart, these efforts aim to lift people out of poverty (SDG 1), ensure women have equal access to opportunities (SDG 5), and create fair chances for everyone to participate in economic growth and decent work (SDG 8). What makes this even stronger is the backing from global initiatives like the World Bank's Universal Financial Access 2030, which highlights the need for financial systems that truly serve everyone especially those who have long been left out of formal finance (World Bank, 2023; United Nations, 2015). In line with this direction, *Tanzania's National Financial Inclusion Framework (2023–2028)* aims to achieve 85 percent inclusion by 2028. It places strong focus on gender-responsive digital finance, consumer protection, and financial literacy to ensure that all groups can participate fairly.

However, persistent demographic disparities raise key questions: *Who is included, who remains excluded, and why?* This study argues that understanding financial inclusion requires looking beyond national averages to explore how demographic attributes like age, gender, education, income, and individuals' residences shape financial participation. These are not background characteristics; they are central forces that determine how inclusive and sustainable a financial system can be.

Using secondary data from FinScope Tanzania (2023), Bank of Tanzania reports, the World Bank Global Findex (2021), the National Bureau of Statistics, GSMA Mobile Money metrics, and primary data from 400 respondents, this study examines how demographic variables affect financial inclusion in Tanzania. By connecting social structures with technological change, the research offers a deeper thoughtful on how different groups participate in acquiring financial services.

Ultimately, the study adds both academic and policy debates by presenting a demographically informed view of financial inclusion. It argues that sustainable inclusion is not achieved through technology alone but through recognizing human diversity how age, gender, education, income, and geography influence financial behavior. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for Tanzania's goal of creating a truly inclusive, digitally empowered economy where every citizen can participate in and benefit from financial development.

A. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The study seeks to understand why financial inclusion in Tanzania remains uneven, even as access to mobile money and other formal services expands. It focuses on how people's age, gender, income, education, and place of residence shape their ability to participate in the financial system, highlighting the persistent gaps faced by women, older adults, low-income groups, and rural populations. By examining these demographic patterns and the structural challenges behind them, the study aims to clarify who continues to be left out and what factors limit fair and meaningful access to financial services.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. THEORETICAL REVIEW

1) *Conceptualizing financial inclusion:*

Financial inclusion is recognised as central to economic progress and an important tool for reducing poverty in developing economies. As noted by the World Bank (2023), it requires that individuals and enterprises have access to affordable and appropriate financial services, including savings, credit, payments, and insurance, that can meet their day-to-day demands as well as their future aspirations. By enabling people to manage risks, accumulate assets, and plan for the future, financial inclusion enhances participation in the formal economy and contributes to broader goals of inclusive and sustainable development.

True financial inclusion is not simply about opening the door to financial services. It also means ensuring that people can use these services regularly, that the services are of good quality, and that they remain affordable. As Allen, Demirgüç-Kunt, Klapper, and Peria (2022) emphasize, genuine inclusion is achieved when financial systems respond to diverse human needs, enabling individuals to participate more fully in the economy while building resilience against future challenges.

In Tanzania, financial inclusion has evolved from a policy objective into a driver of economic transformation. FinScope Tanzania (2023) reports that formal inclusion increased from 44% in 2009 to 76% in 2023, largely due to digital innovations such as mobile money, agent banking, and fintech partnerships that have extended services to rural and low-income groups (Bank of Tanzania [BoT], 2023). The government's initiatives including the *National Financial Inclusion Frameworks I & II* (BoT, 2013–2016; 2018–2022), the *National Financial Education Framework* (2021–2026), and the *National Digital Economy Framework* (2023) have further strengthened access, literacy, and digital ecosystems.

Despite these advances, financial inclusion remains uneven across gender, income, and location, underscoring the need to understand how demographic and social factors continue to shape participation in Tanzania's financial system.

2) *Theoretical foundations of financial inclusion:*

Two major theoretical perspectives explain financial inclusion: Financial Intermediation Theory and Sen's Capability Approach. Financial Intermediation Theory (Diamond, 1984; Levine, 2021) emphasizes how financial institutions connect savers and borrowers, reduce transaction costs, and improve capital allocation. Accessible intermediaries like microfinance institutions, mobile money and banks providers are therefore crucial to inclusive finance (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2022).

Sen's Capability Approach (Sen, 1999; Alkire, 2019) broadens the concept by focusing on the ability of the people and the freedom to use financial services effectively. It highlights the significance of financial literacy, the power of making decision and accessibility to resources. When inequalities in gender, education, or income persist, individuals may have access but lack the real capability to benefit from financial services (Allen et al., 2022; World Bank, 2023).

A behavioural finance perspective further explains how individual attitudes, risk perceptions, and trust in institutions influence financial participation (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014; BoT, 2022). Inclusion, therefore, involves not only structural access but also psychological readiness and confidence.

Together, these theories suggest that sustainable inclusion requires both institutional accessibility and individual empowerment. They form a useful foundation for analysing how demographic factors shape financial behavior in Tanzania.

3) *Demographic factors and financial inclusion in Tanzania:*

Attributes of the demographic such as age, gender, income, education, occupation, and location significantly influence patterns of financial inclusion in Tanzania. These characteristics determine how individuals perceive, access, and use financial services (Njau, 2021; Rubangura, 2022).

Gender remains a persistent barrier. Cultural norms, limited asset ownership, and low financial literacy continue to constrain women's participation. FinScope Tanzania (2023) reports that 26% of women remain financially excluded compared to 17.9% of men. Across Africa, similar gender gaps are shaped by social norms and a lack of identification documents (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022). Targeted interventions such as digital literacy, mobile banking, and group lending can enhance women's access and financial confidence (Allen et al., 2022; FinScope Tanzania, 2023).

Age also shapes inclusion. Younger adults (18–35) adopt digital finance quickly but often lack stable income or credit history, limiting access to complex products (Swam, 2023). Older adults tend to rely on traditional banking methods due to limited digital literacy (Noelia, 2019). BoT (2023) notes that youth constitute about 64% of mobile money users, though their engagement with advanced services like insurance remains low. Expanding financial education and youth-oriented programs can strengthen intergenerational inclusion (Isaga, 2025).

Education strongly correlates with inclusion. Individuals with secondary or higher education are more confident in managing finances and using digital services (Beck et al., 2022; Bruhn & Love, 2022). FinScope (2023) found that Tanzanians with higher education are nearly twice as likely to hold formal financial accounts. The *National Financial Education Framework (2021–2026)* promotes financial literacy through schools and adult programs (BoT, 2022), reinforcing education's role in building trust and economic resilience (Mndolwa & Alhassan, 2020).

Income and occupation determine access to financial products. High-income earners use a broader range of services, while low-income individuals depend on informal mechanisms such as *vikoba* and mobile money (Rubangura, 2022; World Bank, 2023). In Tanzania's informal economy, irregular earnings and lack of collateral restrict credit access (FinScope Tanzania, 2023). Innovative models such as microcredit, pay-as-you-go systems, and agricultural insurance can improve inclusion among informal workers (Ndanshau & Njau, 2021).

Geographic location further shapes inclusion outcomes. Rural residents face challenges such as long distances to banks, poor infrastructure, and limited digital connectivity (BoT, 2023). Only 48% of rural adults are formally included compared to 82% in urban areas (FinScope, 2023). Mobile platforms like M-Pesa and Tigo Pesa have helped reduce this divide, though disparities persist due to uneven agent networks (Were et al., 2021). Expanding rural digital infrastructure and agent coverage is essential for equitable inclusion (Asongu et al., 2023; Giday, 2023).

4) *Digital finance as an impetus for the expansion of financial inclusion:*

The spread of Digital Financial Services (DFS) has redefined financial access across Tanzania, making it more inclusive and dynamic. Active mobile money accounts rose from 11 million in 2013 to over 43 million in 2023, supported by more than 400,000 agents nationwide (BoT, 2023). Mobile platforms have reduced cost and distance barriers, allowing low-income and rural populations to make payments, save, and access credit (GSMA, 2022).

Tanzania's fintech ecosystem is also expanding, offering digital microcredit, micro-insurance, and savings apps tailored to informal sectors (FSDT, 2023; GSMA, 2023). These innovations connect finance with agriculture, women's savings groups, and youth entrepreneurship, extending inclusion beyond basic transactions.

However, many users still rely on mobile money for simple transfers rather than for saving or borrowing (Njau, 2021), limiting long-term financial empowerment (FSDT & BoT, 2023). Barriers such as low digital literacy, cyber risks, and gender disparities in digital usage persist (Swam, 2023). Therefore, digital finance should complement broader strategies that strengthen financial capability, trust, and security to achieve genuine inclusion.

B. *EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM AFRICAN CONTEXTS*

Evidence from across Africa reinforces how demographic attributes shape financial inclusion outcomes. In Kenya, mobile money revolutionized financial participation. Mbiti and Weil (2016) found that M-Pesa improved household welfare and reduced dependence on informal systems, especially among women and rural users. Their findings demonstrate that digital finance can bridge gender and regional gaps when supported by strong infrastructure (Lashitew et al., 2019).

In Ghana, education and gender equality have been key drivers of inclusion. Asongu (2017) found that higher literacy levels and female empowerment correlate with greater financial participation. Education enhances awareness and decision-making, turning access into empowerment (Asongu & Odhiambo, 2020).

In Nigeria, income and geographic inequality continue to hinder access. Okoye et al. (2020) reported that urban and high-income groups use formal services more frequently, while low-income populations depend on informal savings networks. These disparities mirror Tanzania's rural-urban divide (Eshun, 2025).

Across Sub-Saharan Africa, income, education, and gender remain the most influential determinants of inclusion (World Bank, 2023; Wanzala, 2025). Eshun's (2025) cross-country study covering 31 nations found that literacy, income, and urban residence increase the likelihood of financial inclusion, while informality and low education lead to exclusion.

For Tanzania, these regional experiences highlight both opportunities and challenges. Like Kenya, Tanzania benefits from digital innovation but faces structural and educational barriers similar to Nigeria and Ghana. Addressing demographic inequalities and behavioural constraints is essential for translating digital access into real empowerment. Moreover, emerging priorities such as inclusive green finance and climate-resilient financial products remain underexplored but present new frontiers for inclusive growth (CGAP, 2024; UNEP, 2023).

C. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig. 1 Demographic factors and influence on financial inclusion
Source: Author

From this conceptual framework in figure 1, the study assumes that financial inclusion in Tanzania is shaped by basic demographic features. Factors like gender, income, age, and education influence how people access and use financial services and how they adopt financial innovations (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022; World Bank, 2023). These characteristics form the independent variables and are expected to affect financial inclusion directly and indirectly.

Age influences financial behavior, with younger people often more open to digital services and older individuals preferring traditional options (GSMA, 2021). Gender differences may reflect social and economic barriers that limit women’s financial participation (Allen et al., 2020). Education improves people’s ability to understand and use financial products, while income shapes their capacity to save, borrow, or maintain accounts (OECD, 2019). Together, these demographic factors determine who becomes financially included or excluded.

The framework also recognizes the role of mediating factors such as financial literacy, access to financial service points, and economic opportunities. These elements help explain why people with similar demographic profiles may experience different financial outcomes. For example, individuals with higher financial literacy or easier access to financial providers have an ability to use formal financial institutions at the right time (Atkinson & Messy, 2013).

Financial inclusion, the dependent variable, is understood through three aspects: how easily people can access services, how frequently they use them, and how well these services meet their needs (Sarma & Pais, 2011). The model suggests that demographic attributes influence these outcomes both directly and through the mediating factors.

The framework highlights that improving financial inclusion requires addressing demographic gaps while strengthening financial literacy, access, and economic opportunities. It offers a clear structure for understanding variations in financial participation across different groups in Tanzania.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. RESEARCH DESIGN

The study implemented a mixed methods research design to investigate how demographic factors influence access to financial services in Tanzania. By integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches, the study aimed to capture both the measurable patterns and the lived realities shaping financial inclusion. Guided by the pragmatic paradigm, this design allows for a balanced understanding that values both numerical evidence and contextual insight (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Möller, 2022). The quantitative part of the study drew on data from the FinScope Tanzania 2023 Survey and additional questionnaires administered to 400 respondents from diverse socio-economic backgrounds. This helped reveal broad trends and relationships between demographic characteristics and levels of financial inclusion across different groups (Koloseni, 2024).

Complementing this, the qualitative component focused on uncovering the human and institutional dimensions often missed by numerical data. Through interviews with financial service providers, policymakers, and selected participants, the study explored barriers such as limited financial literacy, inadequate infrastructure, and cultural factors affecting digital finance adoption. These insights added depth to the quantitative findings, offering a clearer understanding of how social and structural issues shape financial inclusion. By merging both strands of data, the study provided a more complete and context-sensitive picture of financial inclusion in Tanzania, supporting the formulation of inclusive and evidence-based policies (Magambo, 2024; Nzilano, 2025).

1) *Data analysis:*

The research adopted quantitative and qualitative analytical approaches to understand how demographic attributes influence financial inclusion across different population groups in Tanzania.

Quantitative data were drawn from two main sources: the FinScope Tanzania 2023 Survey and structured questionnaires administered to 400 respondents. Prior to analysis, all data were carefully cleaned, coded, and processed using SPSS and Microsoft Excel to ensure accuracy and consistency. Frequencies, percentages, and mean values were employed to describe the respondents' profiles, covering attributes like age, gender, education level, income, and geographic location. These measures also helped illustrate key indicators of financial inclusion, particularly access, usage, and quality of financial services produced. This stage provided an essential overview of how demographic differences shape participation in financial systems across Tanzania (FinScope Tanzania, 2023; BoT, 2023).

The study applied inferential statistical techniques to explore the relationships between demographic variables and financial inclusion outcomes. In order to assess the strength and direction of the relationships, correlation, chi-square, and binary logistic regression analyses were performed. The logistic regression model was particularly useful in predicting the probability of financial inclusion as influenced by demographic attributes. The findings revealed that education and income play a significant role in enhancing financial participation, while gender disparities and rural residence continue to pose major challenges. These results are consistent with recent studies emphasizing ongoing demographic inequalities in financial access and usage across Tanzania (Isack, Kilindo, & Nyoni, 2023; Osuma, 2025).

The qualitative data obtained from key informant interviews were examined using a thematic analysis approach. All responses were transcribed, coded, and organized into major themes, including barriers to financial access, trust in digital financial systems, and policy and regulatory challenges. This approach made it possible to uncover the deeper social and institutional factors influencing financial inclusion issues that are often beyond the reach of numerical analysis. The themes highlighted how social perceptions, infrastructure gaps, and institutional practices either promote or hinder participation in formal financial systems (Msangi, 2025; Nzilano, 2025).

By combining the quantitative and qualitative results, the study achieved a richer and more balanced understanding of financial inclusion in Tanzania. While the quantitative analysis identified measurable patterns and relationships, the qualitative findings explained the context and motivations behind them. Together, these insights provided a stronger basis for designing inclusive financial policies and strategies, offering practical guidance for policymakers, regulators, and financial systems striving to increase equitable access to financial products.

2) *Participants of the study:*

The study drew on both primary and secondary data to develop a comprehensive and realistic view of how financial systems operate in Tanzania. The primary data came from 400 adult respondents in Dar es Salaam, chosen through a stratified random sampling method. Including participants from the country's main urban and commercial center helped gather valuable insights into financial behaviors in areas where access to digital finance and formal financial systems are most advanced. The secondary data were sourced from the Finscope Tanzania 2023 Survey, which covered 10,000 adults across urban and rural settings. This nationally representative dataset complemented the primary data by offering a wider view of financial inclusion patterns and demographic characteristics throughout the country.

Sampling for both datasets considered key demographic factors such as region, gender, and income level, ensuring fair representation and reducing bias. The study applied a margin of error of 5% and a confidence interval of 95% in line with recognized social research standards (Lohr, 2021). These parameters strengthened the accuracy and reliability of the findings, ensuring that the results reflected Tanzania's diverse population in a credible manner.

3) *Data collection instruments and tests:*

To gather comprehensive and reliable data, the study employed multiple instruments. Structured questionnaires were the principal data collection tool, designed to collect quantitative data on individuals' financial access, usage patterns, and the barriers they face in engaging with financial services. The questionnaire items were designed to capture specific indicators consistent with the Global Findex framework as explained by Demirgüç-Kunt et al. (2018). This framework provides a comprehensive basis for measuring financial inclusion by assessing various dimensions of individuals' financial engagement. Accordingly, the study considered indicators such as ownership of bank and mobile money accounts, access to and use of credit, regularity of savings habits, and uptake of insurance products. These measures allowed for an objective evaluation of the extent to which different demographic groups in Tanzania participate in and benefit from formal and digital financial systems (The Global Findex Database 2025).

In addition to the survey data, semi-structured interviews were conducted with financial service providers and policymakers to obtain in-depth qualitative insights. These interviews contextualised the quantitative findings by highlighting practical challenges and opportunities within the financial inclusion landscape of Tanzania. To further support the analysis, secondary data from academic research, government reports, and policy documents were also incorporated, providing historical and comparative context. To ensure validity, all instruments were pre-tested through a pilot study to identify and correct ambiguous or unclear questions. Expert reviews were also conducted to confirm content relevance and alignment with the study's objectives.

B. *VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY*

Maintaining strong validity and reliability in the research instruments was crucial for preserving the study's credibility, particularly as it investigates how age, gender, education, employment, and income shape financial inclusion in Tanzania. Because financial behaviours differ widely across socio-economic groups, the data collection tools had to be precise and sensitive enough to capture people's everyday experiences with financial services.

Validity focused on how well the instruments measured what they were intended to measure, namely the nuanced ways in which demographic factors influence financial access and usage. To enhance this, a pilot study was conducted with a sample group resembling the target population. This pre-testing phase helped identify ambiguities, culturally inappropriate phrasing, and conceptually misaligned items. Based on participant feedback, the instruments were refined to ensure clarity, contextual relevance, and alignment with the study’s objectives. Additionally, expert reviews were sought from professionals in financial research and survey methodology. Their insights helped confirm the content validity of the instruments, ensuring that each item meaningfully represented key dimensions of financial inclusion, such as trust in financial institutions, digital literacy, and access to formal credit.

Reliability, on the other hand, ensured that the instruments produced consistent and stable results across different contexts and respondents. Standardized procedures were implemented during data collection, and all enumerators received training to minimize bias and maintain uniformity in administering questionnaires and interviews. Internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach’s alpha, with a coefficient of 0.7 or above regarded as acceptable. This statistical measure confirmed that the items within each construct, such as financial behavior, access patterns, and demographic characteristics, were coherently linked and reliably measured. Repeated testing and cross-validation of responses further reinforced the reliability of the findings.

Together, these methodological safeguards ensured that the study’s conclusions are both credible and replicable. By grounding the research in valid and reliable instruments, the analysis offers a trustworthy account of how demographic attributes influence financial inclusion outcomes in Tanzania, providing a solid foundation for policy recommendations and future research.

IV. RESULTS

This study used data from the FinScope Tanzania 2023 Survey, which included a representative sample of 10,000 adults. With a margin of error of 5% and a confidence interval of 95%, the survey provided reliable insights into the financial behaviors of Tanzanians from various demographic and geographic backgrounds. The analysis assessed how differences in age, gender, income, education, and geographic location shape individuals’ participation in various financial inclusion dimensions, including formal service access, digital finance usage, and engagement in savings, credit, and insurance. The findings from the FinScope dataset show that demographic and socioeconomic factors significantly affect financial inclusion outcomes in Tanzania. Urban residents, men, and those with higher levels of education and income were far more likely to access formal financial services than rural populations and individuals with limited education or lower earnings.

Additional primary data collected from 400 respondents in Dar es Salaam support these national patterns while offering deeper insights into the urban context. The results show that almost nine in ten respondents about 90 percent reported access to at least one formal financial service. This high level of inclusion is largely attributed to the widespread use of mobile payment systems and the growing adoption of digital banking in the city. Younger and more educated participants reported higher usage rates of mobile money services and online banking, showing that digital skills and education significantly affect financial inclusion in urban areas. Respondents mentioned convenience, accessibility, and trust in mobile service providers as major reasons for using digital financial tools. Overall, both data sources reveal a clear pattern: financial inclusion in Tanzania is strongly influenced by demographic and socioeconomic differences. While national data reveal broad disparities, the Dar es Salaam results highlight how education, digital access, and income can enhance inclusion in urban settings. These findings emphasize the need for targeted policies that close the rural-urban gap, support women’s financial empowerment, and promote digital skills to ensure wider participation in Tanzania’s changing financial landscape.

A. AGE DISTRIBUTION AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Fig. 2 Age vs. Finance Access
Source: Author

The age-based analysis in figure 2 shows clear differences in financial inclusion among Tanzanian adults. Individuals aged 36–55 years, representing 35% of the sample, recorded the highest inclusion rate (78%). This group’s stronger participation likely reflects steady income, economic stability, and established financial habits gained through years of work and family responsibilities.

The 18–35 years group forms the largest share (40%) of respondents but has a moderate inclusion rate (65%). Despite being familiar with digital technologies, many young adults still face barriers such as low income, unstable jobs, and limited financial literacy, which restrict their engagement with formal financial services.

Older adults aged 56 years and above, who make up 25% of respondents, show the lowest inclusion rate (58%). Their low participation is linked to limited digital skills, reduced economic activity, and continued reliance on informal systems. Overall, financial inclusion in Tanzania peaks in middle adulthood and declines among younger and older groups, highlighting the need for age-targeted financial policies and literacy initiatives to promote inclusion across all age categories.

B. GENDER DISTRIBUTION AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Fig. 3 Gender and financial inclusion
Source: Author

The findings in figure 3 show a clear gender gap in access to financial services. Men make up a slightly larger portion of the respondents at 52%. Their financial inclusion rate is 72%, which is much higher than the 58% for women, who account for 48% of the sample. This difference indicates that men are more likely to use formal financial institutions. Several factors may contribute to this gap. These include social norms related to gender, differences in economic independence, and uneven access to financial education and job opportunities. These results highlight the need for strategies that tackle both structural and cultural barriers that limit women’s participation in the financial system. Programs focused on women, such as savings groups, digital financial literacy, and microcredit initiatives, can help close the gender gap and promote fair financial inclusion.

C. INCOME LEVELS AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Fig. 4 Income vs. Finance Access
Source: Author

From the figure 4 above reveals a clear and compelling gradient in financial inclusion across income groups. High-income earners (top 20%) demonstrate the highest financial inclusion rate at 92%, despite representing only 15% of respondents. In contrast, middle-income individuals comprising 50% of the sample show a moderate inclusion rate of 68%, while low-income earners (bottom 30%) exhibit the lowest inclusion rate at 48%.

This pattern highlights a clear and persistent relationship between income and the extent to which individuals can access formal financial services. Individuals with higher incomes tend to participate more actively in formal financial systems, supported by greater economic stability, disposable resources, and better access to financial infrastructure. In contrast, low-income groups often encounter multiple, reinforcing barriers such as affordability constraints, limited financial literacy, and restricted access to formal banking networks that collectively hinder their financial inclusion.

The findings highlight the urgent need for inclusive financial policies that prioritise affordability, accessibility, and tailored outreach for low-income populations. Solutions such as mobile banking, simplified account structures, and community-based financial education can help bridge this gap and promote equitable financial participation.

These findings reveal a strong correlation between income and financial inclusion. Individuals with higher incomes tend to have greater ability and opportunity to access financial services, while low-income individuals face financial and institutional barriers. The findings emphasise the need for affordable and accessible financial products targeting low-income groups to bridge this significant gap.

D. EDUCATION LEVELS AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Fig. 5 Education levels and financial inclusion
Source: Author

The data presented in Figure 5 above underscores the pivotal role of education in shaping financial inclusion outcomes. Individuals with secondary or higher education exhibit the highest inclusion rate at 85%, significantly outperforming those with primary education (56%) and no formal education (34%). This gradient suggests a strong positive correlation between educational attainment and access to financial services.

Education enhances financial literacy, awareness of financial products, and confidence in engaging with formal financial institutions. Those with higher education are more likely to understand financial terms, navigate digital platforms, and meet eligibility criteria for financial products. In contrast, less-educated individuals may face informational, psychological, and procedural barriers that hinder their financial participation.

These findings imply that targeted educational interventions, especially financial literacy campaigns, could substantially improve inclusion rates among underserved groups. Integrating financial education into school curricula, community outreach, and adult learning programs can strengthen individuals' capacity to understand, access, and make meaningful use of financial services.

In conclusion, education is not merely a background variable, it is a strategic lever for inclusive financial development. Bridging educational gaps is essential for achieving equitable access to financial systems and fostering long-term economic resilience. The data highlights education as a critical determinant of financial inclusion. Educated individuals are likely to possess better financial literacy and access to resources. This finding implies that educational programmes, particularly financial literacy campaigns, could play a great role in improving financial inclusion rates among less-educated groups.

E. GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION

TABLE I
GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION VS. FINANCIAL ACCESS

Category	Urban (%)	Rural (%)
Geographic Distribution of Respondents	60.0	40.0
Access to Financial Services	80.0	52.0

Source: Author

The data in Table 1 highlight a clear difference in financial inclusion between urban and rural populations. Urban residents make up the majority of respondents (60%) and exhibit a high inclusion rate of 80%, while rural residents, representing 40% of respondents, show a lower inclusion rate of 52%.

This pattern reflects the uneven distribution of financial infrastructure and services across regions. Urban areas generally have easier access to banks, mobile money agents, and digital financial platforms, making it simpler for people to open accounts, save, or make transactions. In contrast, many rural communities face challenges such as limited banking facilities, poor network coverage, and higher transaction costs, which restrict an access to financial products.

These findings emphasise that, there is a need for targeted efforts to improve financial access in rural regions. Expanding mobile banking networks, promoting digital literacy, and supporting community-based financial initiatives can help reduce this urban–rural gap. By strengthening rural financial infrastructure, policymakers can move closer to achieving inclusive financial growth that benefits all citizens, regardless of where they live.

F. CROSS-TABULATION ANALYSIS

TABLE II
GENDER AND EDUCATION VS. FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Gender	Education Level	% Financially Included
Female	Secondary or Higher	78%
Male	Secondary or Higher	92%

Source: Author

The cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 2 examines the intersection of gender and educational attainment in relation to financial inclusion. The bar chart clearly illustrates that while secondary or higher education significantly enhances financial inclusion for both men and women, notable disparities persist between genders.

Men with secondary education or higher exhibit a financial inclusion rate of 92%, compared to 78% for similarly educated women. This 14 percentage point gap suggests that education alone does not fully mitigate gender-based barriers to financial access. While both groups benefit from higher education, the differential outcomes imply that structural and systemic factors, such as cultural norms, institutional biases, and differential access to financial products continue to disadvantage women.

This finding reinforces the need for gender-sensitive financial inclusion strategies. Policymakers should not only promote educational attainment but also address the underlying social and institutional constraints that inhibit women's full participation in financial systems. Interventions may include targeted financial literacy programmes, inclusive product design, and regulatory reforms that promote gender equity in financial services.

In summary, while education is a powerful enabler of financial inclusion, it must be complemented by deliberate efforts to dismantle gender-specific barriers. The graph serves as a compelling visual representation of this nuanced dynamic, emphasising the importance of intersectional analysis in financial inclusion research.

G. PREDICTORS OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION

TABLE III
CALCULATED (PREDICTORS OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION)

Predictor	Odds Ratio	Coefficient (β)	Statistical Significance	Interpretation
Income	1.5	0.405	$P < 0.01$	Strong positive predictor
Education	2.3	0.833	$P < 0.01$	Very strong positive predictor
Gender (male)	1.4	0.336	$P < 0.05$	Moderate positive predictor
Geographic (urban)	1.8	0.588	$P < 0.01$	Strong positive predictor

Fig. 6 Financial inclusion’s predictors
Source: Author

The multinomial probit results in Figure 6 show that four demographic factors income, education, gender, and geographic location significantly predict financial inclusion. All four variables are positively associated with the likelihood of being financially included. The lines and bar charts visually highlight these relationships, allowing a clear comparison of how strongly each factor contributes to financial inclusion.

Education stands out as the strongest predictor. Individuals with secondary education or higher are 2.3 times more likely to be financially included ($p < 0.01$). This finding emphasizes the value of education in shaping financial awareness and the ability to use formal financial services. It also suggests that expanding access to quality education may considerably improve financial inclusion levels.

Geographic location also has a notable influence. Urban residents are 1.8 times more likely to be financially included compared to rural residents ($p < 0.01$). This gap reflects the persistent differences in infrastructure and service availability between urban and rural areas, including limited bank branches, weaker digital networks, and fewer financial outreach initiatives in rural communities. Reducing these geographic disparities is therefore crucial for promoting inclusive financial development.

Income is another strong predictor, with each decile increase in income associated with a 1.5 times greater likelihood of financial inclusion ($p < 0.01$). This indicates that financial inclusion is closely tied to economic capacity, as individuals with higher-incomes are more likely to afford and utilise financial products. It also highlights the need for pro-poor financial policies and subsidised services to reach lower-income populations.

Gender differences are evident, with men being 1.4 times more likely to be financially included than women ($p < 0.05$). This finding points to persistent gender-based barriers in financial access, including cultural norms, mobility constraints, and lower financial literacy among women. Gender-sensitive financial inclusion strategies such as targeted outreach, digital solutions, and inclusive product design are necessary to close this gap.

The statistical significance of these predictors supports the formulation of targeted policy interventions. Enhancing education, bridging urban-rural divides, promoting income equity, and addressing gender disparities are critical steps toward achieving comprehensive financial inclusion. The graph serves as a visual reinforcement of these findings, aiding in the communication of complex statistical relationships to diverse audiences.

V. DISCUSSION

The study highlights effects of the demographic attributes on the financial products in Tanzania, with income emerging as a key determinant. The positive association observed is consistent as explained by Karlan et al. (2014), who noted that higher-income individuals are better positioned to engage with formal financial services. The study suggests that financial resources remain a key determinant of access, particularly in contexts where poverty limits financial participation among low-income groups. Education was also shown to enhance financial inclusion, reinforcing an argument that financial literacy is a crucial driver of financial participation (Ruth et al., 2020). Educated individuals are more capable of understanding the benefits of financial products and navigating the complexities of the financial system, underscoring the need for financial literacy initiatives in rural and marginalised communities.

Gender disparities further illustrate the uneven nature of financial inclusion, as women face structural and cultural barriers, lower income levels, and limited financial education, which restrict their participation in formal financial services (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). Addressing these disparities requires targeted policies that promote women's economic empowerment, improved access to tailored financial products and raise the financial literacy levels. In addition, the results indicate that financial systems can be improved through interventions such as microloans, digital financial literacy programmes for youth, simplified products for the elderly, and strengthened financial infrastructure in rural areas (Allen et al., 2016).

Although the study produces important findings, it is limited by its cross-sectional design, which reflects financial inclusion at only one point in time and therefore cannot capture long-term developments or establish causality. Reliance on self-reported data can potentially lead to bias in the findings, while the omission of marginalised populations, such as individuals in hard to reach areas or those with disabilities, limits the broader applicability of the results. Despite these limitations, the study makes a valuable contribution by underscoring the influence of demographic factors like income, education, and gender on financial inclusion in developing countries. Moreover, it offers practical guidance for policymakers seeking to promote equality and extend financial access to all segments of society in Tanzania.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study explains remarkable disparities in financial inclusion across different demographic groups in Tanzania, attributes like gender, income, age, geographical location and education emerged to be a key of demographic determinants. The evidence reveals that while access to financial services has expanded largely through mobile and digital platforms significant inequalities persist, particularly among women, low-income earners, and rural populations. The findings show that there is a need for inclusive strategies that can help to expand access and address the structural and socio-economic barriers limiting participation in formal financial systems.

To bridge the financial inclusion gap, policy efforts should prioritize the promotion of digital and financial literacy, especially among underserved communities, and the development of affordable, context-appropriate financial products tailored to their unique needs. Strengthening both digital and physical financial infrastructure in remote areas is also essential to ensure equitable access and sustainability. Collaborative efforts between government institutions, financial service providers, and community organizations can play a critical role in advancing these goals.

Future study should adopt longitudinal approaches to capture the growing nature of the financial systems over time and to evaluate the effectiveness of specific policy interventions targeting marginalized groups. Moreover, employing qualitative research approaches could provide in-depth perspectives on the experiences and challenges faced by key demographic groups, particularly women, youth, and rural populations thereby deepening understanding of the contextual dynamics influencing financial inclusion. Such comprehensive inquiry would not only advance academic knowledge but also inform evidence-based policies and practices aimed at achieving inclusive, equitable, and sustainable financial systems.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Alkire, S. (2019). *The capability approach and human development*. Oxford University Press.
- [2] Allen, F., Carletti, E., & Qiao, Y. (2022). Youth exclusion from formal financial systems: Barriers and challenges in sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Financial Inclusion*, 8(3), 45–63.
- [3] Allen, F., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., & Peria, M. S. M. (2016). The foundations of financial inclusion: Understanding ownership and use of formal accounts. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 27, 1–30.
- [4] Allen, F., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., & Peria, M. S. M. (2022). The foundations of financial inclusion: Understanding access, usage, and quality of financial services. *Journal of Financial Development Studies*, 14(2), 101–117.
- [5] Asongu, S. A., & Nwachukwu, J. C. (2023). Urban–rural divide in financial inclusion: Evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Financial Economics*, 12(4), 123–145.
- [6] Bank of Tanzania. (2021). *Annual report: Financial inclusion in Tanzania 2021*. <https://www.bot.go.tz>
- [7] Bank of Tanzania. (2022). *Financial sector reform progress and outlook*. <https://www.bot.go.tz>
- [8] Bank of Tanzania. (2023). *Annual financial inclusion report 2023*. Bank of Tanzania.
- [9] Beck, T., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Levine, R. (2022). Education and financial inclusion: Evidence from emerging markets. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 26(2), 256–270.
- [10] Bruhn, M., & Love, I. (2022). The impact of financial inclusion on economic development in low-income countries. *Development Economics Review*, 15(2), 88–103.
- [11] Delvin, M. (2022). Barriers to financial inclusion in sub-Saharan Africa: A study of Tanzania. *African Financial Studies*, 20(3), 50–68.
- [12] Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Peria, M. S. (2022). Gender and financial inclusion: The role of financial literacy and mobile banking in developing countries. *Journal of Financial Services Research*, 12(5), 149–173.
- [13] Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., & Singer, D. (2023). *The global state of financial inclusion 2023: Access to financial services and inclusion outcomes*. World Bank Publications. <https://www.worldbank.org>
- [14] Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., Singer, D., Ansar, S., & Hess, J. (2018). *The Global Findex Database 2017: Measuring financial inclusion and the fintech revolution*. World Bank.
- [15] Diamond, D. W. (1984). Financial intermediation and delegated monitoring. *Review of Economic Studies*, 51(3), 393–414.
- [16] Dupas, P., & Robinson, J. (2023). Bridging barriers to financial inclusion in Tanzania: A holistic approach. *World Development*, 121, 104–119.
- [17] FinScope Tanzania. (2021). *Financial inclusion in Tanzania: Key findings from the FinScope Survey 2021*. <https://www.finscope.co.tz>
- [18] FinScope Tanzania. (2023). *National financial inclusion survey report 2023*. Financial Sector Deepening Trust.
- [19] Giday, S. (2023). Digital infrastructure and rural financial inclusion in East Africa. *African Journal of Development Studies*, 29(1), 77–95.
- [20] Greene, W. H. (2018). *Econometric analysis* (8th ed.). Pearson Education.
- [21] GSMA. (2022). *Mobile money and financial inclusion: The role of technology in Tanzania*. <https://www.gsma.com>
- [22] Karlan, D., Ratan, A. L., & Zinman, J. (2014). Savings, credit, and financial inclusion: Evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Development Economics*, 108, 47–60.
- [23] Koloseni, D. (2024). Expediting financial inclusion in Tanzania using FinTech: Evidence from rural and remote communities. *Technology in Society*, 78, 102880.
- [24] Lashitew, A. A., van Tulder, R., & Liasse, Y. (2019). What explains the diffusion of mobile money innovations? *Research Policy*, 48(5), 1201–1215.

- [25] Levine, R. (2021). Finance and growth: Theory and evidence. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 35(4), 89–110.
- [26] Mndolwa, E., & Alhassan, A. (2020). Financial capability and inclusive finance in sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of African Business*, 21(2), 159–179.
- [27] Mori, N., & Mlambiti, R. (2020). Determinants of customers' adoption of mobile banking in Tanzania: Further evidence from a diffusion of innovation theory. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management, and Innovation*, 16(2), 1–20.
- [28] Njau, S. (2021). Financial inclusion in Tanzania: Policy and progress towards universal access by 2030. *African Journal of Finance and Development*, 3(2), 24–37.
- [29] Noelia, R. (2019). The economic benefits of financial inclusion in low-income countries. *Journal of Economic Development*, 22(4), 12–25.
- [30] Rubangura, M. (2022). Financial inclusion and poverty reduction: A policy perspective for Tanzania. *Journal of Development Policy*, 19(1), 77–89.
- [31] Ruth, L., Ndiege, B. O., & Mushi, G. (2020). Financial literacy and financial inclusion in developing countries: The case of Tanzania. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 15(2), 281–301.
- [32] Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). Free Press.
- [33] Sen, A. (1999). *Development as freedom*. Oxford University Press.
- [34] Swam, K. (2023). Financial inclusion and its impact on economic growth: A review of sub-Saharan Africa. *African Economic Review*, 42(1), 88–101.
- [35] Were, M., Ngugi, R., & Kirimi, L. (2021). Drivers of financial inclusion gaps in sub-Saharan Africa: Evidence from Kenya and Tanzania. *Development Practice Journal*, 31(5), 653–670.
- [36] World Bank. (2021). *The World Bank financial inclusion report: Tanzania country profile 2021*. <https://www.worldbank.org>
- [37] World Bank. (2022). *Financial inclusion as a tool for poverty alleviation: The case of Tanzania*. <https://www.worldbank.org>
- [38] World Bank. (2023a). *Global Findex Database 2023: Financial inclusion, digital payments, and resilience in the global economy*. World Bank Publications.
- [39] World Bank. (2023b). *Tanzania economic update: Building back better through inclusive finance*. World Bank Publications.